

Reaction of 2-bromo-3-keto triterpenoids : Deoxygenation and simultaneous debromination by Huang-Minlon reduction condition

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Manuscript received 11 November 2010, revised 09 March 2012, accepted 07 June 2012

Abstract : On heating 2 α -bromo/2,2-dibromo lupanone (1/1a) and 2 α -bromo/4 α -bromo friedelin (2/2a) with diethylene glycol and hydrazine hydrate (Huang-Minlon modified Wolff-Kishner reaction) under reflux produced lupane (3) and friedelane (4), respectively.

Keywords : 2-Bromo-3-keto triterpenoids, diethylene glycol, hydrazine hydrate.

Introduction

The Wolff-Kishner reduction has been extensively used for deoxygenating aldehyde and ketone functions to methyl and methylene¹⁻⁵. Recently, Furrow *et al.* suggested that carbonyl compounds are reduced to methylene via *N*-tert-butylidimethylsilylhydrazones in a very good yield⁶. Wolfson *et al.* reduced carbonyl compound to methylene in a greener approach using glycerol as a solvent using Wolff-Kishner reaction⁷. Similar types of reduction takes place in household microwave but there have been reports of significant decrease in shorter reaction time⁸. In continuation of our studies on the reaction of 2-bromo-3-keto triterpenoids⁹⁻¹¹ and in order to check the effect of α -halogen atom/atoms on the reduction of carbonyl compound by Wolff-Kishner or modified Wolff-Kishner methods, we have carried out studies on the reduction of 2 α -bromo-3-keto triterpenoids by using Huang-Minlon modified Wolff-Kishner reduction, taking 2 α -bromo-3-keto compounds of pentacyclic triterpenoids of lupane and friedelin skeletons. Contrary to our expectation, we observed that there is simultaneous deoxygenation and debromination in the process. Similar results were observed for all the bromoketones used in the present investigation.

Although there exist a number of methods for dehalogenation process¹²⁻¹⁷, reduction involving deoxygenation accompanied by dehalogenation of α -haloketones under Huang-Minlon modified Wolff-Kishner reduction condition is not yet reported so far.

Results and discussion

2 α -Bromo lupanones (1/1a) and 2 α -bromo friedelin/4 α -bromo friedelin (2/2a) were prepared by the method as reported elsewhere¹⁶ and was characterized by spectral analysis (for compound 1 and 1a) and by comparison with the already reported data (for compound 2 and 2a). Each of 2 α -bromo lupanone (1)¹⁶, 2,2-dibromo lupanone (1a)¹⁶, 2 α -bromofriedelin (2)¹⁷ and 4 α -bromofriedelin (2a)¹⁷ was refluxed with diethylene glycol and hydrazine hydrate for 30 min (Scheme 1).

After addition of KOH the mixture was further refluxed for one hour. After usual workup³, the residue in each case was chromatographed over a column of silica gel and eluted with petroleum ether-toluene (4 : 1) to furnish pure lupane (3) and friedelane (4). These were identified by comparing their m.p.s and by Co-TLC and Co-IR data with those reported in the literature.

Discussion of reaction mechanism :

Conversion of carbonyl to methylene involves the usual Huang-Minlon modified Wolff-Kishner reduction procedure. Once the carbonyl group reduced to methylene the nucleophile attack of lone pair of nitrogen of hydrazine takes place on the electrophilic carbon holding the bromine atoms. This is followed by the elimination of second bromine as HBr with the formation of C=N double bond. The reduction of C-X bond to C-H bond has already been reported in the literature¹⁸⁻²⁰. The subsequent elimination of proton followed by elimination of nitrogen

Scheme 1

converts $>CBr_2$ into $>CH_2$ (Scheme 2). On the other hand, in case of monobromo derivative the nucleophilic attack of hydrazine eliminates the bromide as HBr which is followed by elimination of hydrogen²¹ to generate C=N bond which is subsequently yielded the new methylene group (Scheme 3) as observed in the case of dibromo compound (**1a**) (Scheme 2).

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80 °C) was used during the investigations. IR spectra were recorded in nujol on Beckmann IR-20 spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on 300 MHz Bruker Avance FT-NMR spectrometers using CDCl₃ solution containing TMS as reference. ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on 300 MHz Bruker Avance FT-NMR spectrometer using CDCl₃ solution containing TMS as reference. UV spectra were recorded in methanol on Shimadzu-UV 240 spectrophotometer. Mass spectra were recorded on Varian Mat 711 (70 eV) and JMS-D 300 (70

eV) by EI/CI method. All the rotations were taken in CHCl₃ solution. Column chromatography was performed over silica gel (60–120 mesh, BDH). TLC was performed on chromatoplate of silica gel G (Glaxo and BDH) and the spots were located by exposing to iodine chamber.

General procedure for bromination :

A solution of 3-keto triterpenoids (3 g) in chloroform (150 mL) was mixed with dimethyl sulphoxide (75 mL). *N*-Bromosuccinimide (3.5 g) was then added to it in small lots in order to keep the temperature of the reaction mixture below 25 °C and the mixture kept in dark for 10 days. It was extracted with chloroform and the extract washed several times with water, dried (Na₂SO₄) and solvent removed under reduced pressure. The residue (2.8 g) was chromatographed over a column of silica gel (75 g) developed with petroleum ether. Elution of the column with petroleum ether : toluene (4 : 1) furnished white solids which on crystallization from chloroform-methanol mixture yielded white needle shaped crystalline solids.

Note

Scheme 2

Characterization data of compound 1 :

White crystalline solid, yield 93% (Found : C, 71.20; H, 9.31. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{49}\text{OBr}$ (506) : C, 71.15; H, 9.68%), m.p. 224–225 °C (chloroform-methanol); it showed positive Beilstein test for bromine; IR : 1720 cm^{-1} ; UV : 225 nm ($\epsilon = 7010$), 310 nm ($\epsilon = 42$); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) : characteristic signals appeared at δ 0.77 (6H, s, 2- CH_3), 0.92, 1.10, 1.13, 1.2 (12H, 4s, 4t- CH_3), 0.76 and 0.85 (6H, 2d, 2s- CH_3 , J 7 Hz), 2.65 (1H, dd, 1-C- H_{e} , J 12 and 6 Hz), 2.67 (1H, t, 1C- H_{a} , J 12 Hz), 5.06 (1H, dd, 2- CH_{e} , J 12 and 6 Hz) ppm; in addition the methine protons each at C_5 , C_9 , C_{13} appeared as singlet at δ 0.82, 1.26, 1.62 ppm respectively, whereas those at C_{18} , C_{19} and C_{20} appeared as multiplet centered at δ 1.56, 2.37

and 2.22 ppm respectively; multiplets appeared in the region δ 1.18–1.84 ppm were assigned for the methylene protons attached to C_6 , C_7 , C_8 , C_{11} , C_{15} , C_{16} , C_{21} and C_{22} carbons. The above assignment of the pmr signals was done in comparison to the earlier reports¹⁶. MS : m/z at 506, 504 [M^+], 491, 489 [$\text{M}-\text{CH}_3$]⁺ (1 : 1), 463, 461 [$\text{M}-\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$]⁺ (1 : 1), 426, 425 [$\text{M}-\text{HBr}$]⁺, 285, 283, 274, 206, 191, 163, 149, 123 (100%). It was identified by comparison (mixed m.p., Co-IR, Co-TLC, Co-NMR) with authentic sample of 2 α -bromo lupanone (1) (lit.¹⁷ m.p. 225 °C).

Characterization data of compound 1a :

White crystalline solid, yield 93% (Found : C, 61.47; H, 13.81. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{48}\text{OBr}_2$ (586) : C, 61.43; H,

Scheme 3

13.33%), m.p. 210–211 °C (chloroform-methanol); IR : 1722 (CO) cm⁻¹; UV : 222 nm ($\epsilon = 7928$), 312 nm ($\epsilon = 27$); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : characteristic ¹H NMR signals appeared at δ 0.77, 0.94, 0.97, 1.09, 1.24 (15H, 5s, 5t-CH₃), 0.78 and 0.86 (6H, 2d, 2s-CH₃, *J* 7 Hz), 3.13 and 3.64 (2H, 2d, 1-CH₂, *J* 16 Hz) ppm. Complete assignment of the pmr signals was done in comparison to the earlier reports¹⁶. MS : *m/z* at 586, 584, 582 [M⁺] (1 : 2 : 1), 567, 569, 571 [M-CH₃]⁺, 539, 541, 543 [M-CH(CH₃)₂]⁺ (1 : 2 : 1), 504, 506 [M-HBr]⁺ (1 : 1), 489, 491 [M-HBr-CH₃]⁺ (1 : 1), 461, 463 [M-HBr-CO]⁺ (1 : 1), 426 [M-2Br]⁺ (1 : 1 : 1), 425, 424, 409, 285, 283, 274, 231, 206, 205, 191, 177, 163, 123 (100%). It was identified by comparison (mixed m.p., Co-IR, Co-TLC, Co-

NMR) with an authentic sample of 2,2-dibromo lupanone (**1a**) (lit.¹⁷ m.p. 210 °C).

Characterization data of compound 2 :

White crystalline solid, yield 91% (Found : C, 71.25; H, 9.61. Calcd. for C₃₀H₄₉OBr : C, 71.43; H, 9.68%), m.p. 214 °C (chloroform-methanol); IR : 1710 (CO) cm⁻¹; MS : *m/z* at 506, 504 [M]⁺ (1 : 1), 491, 489, 427, 426, 382, 380, 354, 353, 351, 301, 300, 273, 205, 179, 137, 135, 125, 123, 109, 95, 69 (base peak). It was identified by comparison (mixed m.p., Co-IR, Co-TLC) with an authentic sample of 2 α -bromo friedelin (**2**) (lit.²² m.p. 210 °C).

Characterization data of compound 2a :

White crystalline solid, yield 91% (Found : C, 71.26; H, 9.65. Calcd. for C₃₀H₄₈OBr₂ (586) : C, 70.44; H,

9.38%), m.p. 198–199 °C (chloroform-methanol); IR : 1710 (CO) cm^{-1} ; it was identified by comparison (mixed m.p., Co-IR, Co-TLC) with an authentic sample of 4 α -bromo friedelin (**2a**) (lit.²² m.p. 196–197 °C).

General procedure for reduction :

Bromo-keto compounds (200 mg) in diethylene glycol (30 mL) were refluxed with hydrazine hydrate (2.3 mL) for 30 min and KOH (200 mg) was added in a 150 ml two-necked round-bottomed flask fitted with a reflux condenser. The reaction mixture was then warmed on a boiling water bath until most of the potassium hydroxide get dissolved and then heated further under reflux for 1 h using a heating mantle. The reflux condenser was then removed and another condenser was fitted downward for distillation. Distillation was continued for 2.5 h until the temperature of the liquid rises to 190 °C. The reaction mixture was then cooled, diluted with water when a solid separated out. The solid (185 mg) dissolved in benzene was poured over a column of silica gel (15 g) developed with petroleum ether. Elution of the column with petroleum ether : toluene (4 : 1) furnished white solids which on crystallization from chloroform-methanol mixture yielded white needle shaped crystalline solids.

Characterization data of compound **3** :

White crystalline solid, yield 95% (Found : C, 87.10; H, 12.58. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{52}$ (412) : C, 87.39; H, 12.62%), m.p. 187–188 °C (chloroform-methanol), $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} - 7.2^\circ$; it did not respond to the tetra nitro methane (TNM) test for active unsaturation and Beilstein test for halogen. IR spectrum of the compound showed no characteristic absorption for functional groups. Finally, it was identified by comparison (mixed m.p., Co-IR, Co-TLC) with an authentic sample of lupane (**3**) (lit.²³ m.p. 188 °C $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} - 7.5^\circ$).

Characterization data of compound **4** :

White crystalline solid, yield 91% (Found : C, 87.50; H, 12.60. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{52}$ (412) : C, 87.30; H, 12.70%), m.p. 248–250 °C (chloroform-methanol), $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} + 21.2^\circ$; it did not respond to the TNM test for active unsaturation and Beilstein test for halogen. IR spectrum of the compound showed no characteristic absorption for functional

groups. It was identified by comparison (mixed m.p., Co-IR, Co-TLC) with an authentic sample of friedelane (**4**) (lit.²⁴ m.p. 251–252 °C $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} + 22^\circ$).

Acknowledgement

The authors thank to CDRI, Lucknow, India, for the mass spectral data and elemental analysis and to UGC, New Delhi, India, for financial support.

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